

TRENDS OF OVER THE COUNTER DRUG USE AMONG PHARMACY AND PHYSIOTHERAPY STUDENTS OF A MEDICAL UNIVERSITY IN PAKISTAN

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Abstract

Objective: Aim of present work was to evaluate the frequency of over the counter (OTC) drugs use between students of two institutes.

Methodology: The descriptive cross sectional was made by a questionnaire; includes simple questions about OTC drug use, total 350 questionnaire were distributed among student of Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences (IPS) and Institute of Physiotherapy and Rehabilitations Sciences (IPRS), People University of Medical and Health Sciences for Women, Nawabshah (SBA). Data were analyzed using SPSS v26.

Results: Various factors depends upon use of OTC drugs were studied, results shows that 218 students prefer to use OTC drugs, prevention of known illness is a prominent factor that attract more to use OTC drugs, as 66% of total students use drug due to this factor.

Conclusion: It can conclude that regulatory authorities should make strict and effective rules to limit OTC use. To educate the community about hazards of non-essential drug use is also need of time.

INTRODUCTION

It is a common experience of human, to face disorder or disease. However, the response of each person to such disorder is different, depending upon various beliefs of individual and some other fundamental factors. The individual responses and activities during any chronic or acute disorder are called self-care. World Health Organization (WHO) appreciates the presence of a vital role of self-medication in curing disorders. Therefore, approaches to explain the appropriateness of self-medication are yet to be structured and enhanced¹. The drugs that can purchase by a person without any prescription or health care personals advice

are called non-prescription drugs or over-the-counter drugs (OTCs). There are currently more than 300000 various OTC drugs available only in US^{2,3}. Since self-medication is mostly symptomatic based and taken without evaluation by qualified health care personals. Self-medication may leads to resolve the problems associated with signs and symptoms of underlying disease, on other hand this may complicate the problem, create drug resistance and delay the diagnosis and cause adverse drug reaction^{1,4,5}. Combining therapy is another problem that healthcare professionals encounter in persons involve in consumption of

OTC drugs. Previous studies revealed, that for sake of profit the OTC industries continue to propagate the ideas that OTCs are completely safe and effective, although health care professionals are frequently giving precautions about extensive use of OTC drugs⁶. From studies on self-medication in developing countries it can be concluded that in different income level population, the irresponsibility of higher authorities and unregulated sales of drugs is to be considered as main reasons of self-medication. Results from previous work on self-medication shows that may results its prevalence in rage of 6.3-76%, in different settings and demographic groups. Above mentioned factors makes medication usage more dangerous for population and should warrant strict policies and make immediate implementation, in order to reduce the problems associated with OTC drugs³. The Population-based studies conducted by researchers in developed countries as United Kingdom, Australia, Scotland and other countries of Asia like Singapore and Taiwan, their results indicate that between a half and two-thirds of the population used nonprescription medicines, includes complementary and OTC medications, while the prevalence of self-medication was found much higher in the developing countries, It is as high as 98% in Palestine⁶⁻⁸. Result from a study conducted in India indicates the prevalence of self-medication was 80.9%⁹. Another study conducted in Pakistan with reference to gender specification, revealed that the prevalence of self-medication in males and females in Karachi was found to be 88.4% and 81.2% respectively⁶. Further studies indicate increase trends of self- medications were found particularly among the youth. These trends can be attributed to socio-economic factors, life style, ready access to drugs, the increased potential to manage certain illnesses through self-care, and greater availability of medicinal products, socio-demographic, epidemiological, unavailability of healthcare professional, relaxation of drug regulatory agencies, society and exposure to advertisement and sufficient information about medicines⁵. Other reasons for self-medication among university students were their previous experiences, recommendation of family or friends,

their health problems being considered as too trivial, non-availability of transport and ability to self-manage the symptoms¹⁰. In developing countries almost every pharmacy sells drugs without a prescription and same phenomenon have been observed in Pakistan. Some habit-forming medicines as benzodiazepines and antibiotics are easily available without prescription for a common person. Availability of some potent drugs coupled with poor awareness may impart certain type of adverse effect which may leads to produce lethal effects on a layman. The lack of a good primary healthcare system associated with cost issues compels the population to approach other avenues instead of healthcare professionals to seek the solution of health related problems. Despite this, there is scarcity of literature regarding self-medication in Pakistan and there is intense need to address this problem⁶.

Keeping in mind the above facts, this study was designed to evaluate trend of the OTC drug use among female students of People University of Medical and Health Sciences, Nawabshah (SBA), to individualized the necessary and unnecessary uses, to compare trends of OTC drug use between Pharmacy and Physiotherapy students and to assess socio demographic determinants of OTC drug use among students.

METHODOLOGY

Study Population

A descriptive cross-sectional study was carried out in People University of Medical and Health Sciences for Women (PUMHSW), Nawabshah, SBA. In this study second to fifth year female students of Pharmacy and Physiotherapy were included; data were collected during the July 2024 to December 2024.

Sampling Technique

Community-based cross-sectional study was initially conducted as a pilot study on 20 volunteers in order to know the limitations of the Performa and it's applicability in female students of Medical University. Some of the questions and wordings in question base Performa were modified based on the understanding and comprehension of information to the students.

Total 350 girls were participated in this study, the two groups were designed and one group was selected from student of pharmacy (175 students) and other from physiotherapy (175). Sample was taken by random sampling method with age of fifteen year and above, data was collected during July 2024 to December 2024. Both Institutes of Medical University running course of 5 year bachelor program. Students of institutes were selected by systemic randomization in order to represent two different institutes. The students which were present at the days of data collection were included. A semi-structured Performa based on simple questionnaire was designed and provided to each consenting individuals. Ethical issues (consent & confidentiality) were taken into account with approval of IRB of PUMHSW. A total of 350 questionnaires were distributed among students and 319 questionnaires were returned back making a response rate of 91.14%, this response rate was observed because 31 students (8.85%) do not returned form, while 11 (3.14%) students showed lack of interest in study and filled form incompletely, which were unable to include in study. Among the forms returned some forms were having minor deficiencies which were checked, and completed by students after a brief description of study giving to students.

Study Tool

A semi structured questionnaire was designed to collect the following data: socio-demographic characteristics of participating, for example, age, gender, residence, marital statuses, institute, phase of study, and their parent educational level. Health-related questions, for example, attitude toward health, current health status, and treatment with or without medical supervision, believe about self-medication convenient drugs

use, source of advice, advantage, disadvantage of self-medication and knowledge about drugs.

Ethical Consideration

This study was approved by Institutional Ethical Review Committee (ERC) at PUMHSW University. A written consent was taken from participants. The student was obtained with assurance of confidentiality and anonymity of the data.

Data Analysis

Data were statistically calculated using the SPSS v26, and discrete variables were presented using their number and percentages.

RESULTS

Demographic characterization is to be considered as an important part of any survey type evaluations. In present’s study this portion includes weigh, age, residency, marital status and parent’s education. This evaluation gives the researcher a clue about influence of socio-demographic factors on their different variable. In present project various demographic characterizations has been conducted. The result of studies revealed that (97%) of the students were unmarried and (3%) married, while among all the students (27%) from the 2nd year, 28% from the 3rd year, (28%) from the 4th year and (18%) from final year. The lowest number of students were in the age group >23 years with a percentage of (3%), while the highest number of students were in the 15-22 years age group with a percentage of (97%). Among the respondents large number of population was from hostel (73%) while (27%) respondent was from local area of Nawabshah (SBA) as shown in Table 1.

TABLE I- Demographic characteristics of respondents.

Items	Sub group	Frequency(n)	Percentage
Marital status	Married	6	3%
	Unmarried	212	97%
Year of study	2 nd Phase	58	27%
	3 rd Phase	61	28%
	4 th Phase	60	28%
	5 th Phase	30	18%

Age group	15-22	213	97%
	>23	5	3%
Residence	Hostler	160	73%
	Locale	58	27%

In present project a survey was conducted about self-medication, among the students of Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences (IPS) and Institute of Physiotherapy and Rehabilitation Sciences (IPRS), People University of Medical and Health Sciences for Women, Nawabshah (PUMHSW). Total number of 350 questioners was distributed among students, while 319 questioners were returned back and entertained in study. Among all 319 participating 218 (68%) students were founded to use OTC medicines. On the other hand 101 (32 %) and they further investigated about reason to not use. Only 36 (23%) students of IPRS did not prefer to use OTC medicines, while 65 (41%) students of IPS did not prefer use of OTC medicine as shown in Figure 1 & 2.

During study various reasons were evaluated that cause the female students not to use OTC medicine, among main and important reason were fear of side effects 51 (51%) students, common believes about medicines that it is injurious to health 31 (31%) students, prior/previous bad experience 12 (12%) students and Lack of knowledge 7 (7%) students as shown in Figure 3.

Weight of person is an important parameter in pharmaceutical sciences, as it helps in calculation dose size and dosage regimen. In this study weight of participating student were also evaluated. Result of study revealed that weight of maximum number (40%) of student fall in range of 50 to 56 kg, the results has been listed in Table-2 and depicted in Figure 4.

TABLE II- Weight frequency.

Weight	Frequency(n)	Percentage
36-48	26	12%
43-49	49	22%
50-56	87	40%
57-63	32	15%
64-70	17	8%
71-77	6	3%
78-85	1	0%

Budget spent by a student on self-medication was another important variable of this project, because cost effective imparts great influence on success rate of particular therapy. From findings obtained from study, it was concluded that most of the students spent 1-10% of their pocket money on OTC medicine 164 students (75%), 11-20% pocket money spent by 24 students (12%), 21-30% spent by 15 students (7%), more than 30% spent by 12 students (6%). The result revealed that self-medication has substantial burden on student’s pocket money.

In developing countries there are various reasons to use OTC drugs, like unavailability of health care professionals, self-medication is considered as money and time saving further the people use medicines by self on behalf of previous successful therapy of OTC.

In present project reasons of self-medication were evaluated critically and result showed that the main reasons for OTC medicines preference among different students Institute were prevention of known illness as shown in (Figure 6) 144 students (66%), followed by successful pre

experience with OTC medicines 33 students (15%) and time saving 21 students (10%), while 15 students (7%) were thinking that disease Frequency of using OTC is also vary with different medical condition of person and severity of disorder/disease like whether the condition is sever, mild or moderate. Present work relates the condition of volunteers with frequency of OTC used. From obtained result it can conclude that, the most common medical conditions that influence the choice of OTC medicines among the studied students were headache 147 students (67%), cough and cold 39 students (18%), fever 19 students (9 %), Acidity 6 students (3%), injury 3 students (1%) of the total cases and others 4 students (2%) as shown in Figure 7.

Each group of drug whether OTC or prescribed having its own therapeutic effect, along with unique side and adverse effect, so it is necessary part of evaluations that which group of drugs are most frequently used in self-medication. This study performed at University of Medical and Health Sciences, having evaluation about various group of drug as integral part. From finding it was observed that the analgesics 89 students (41%), were most common drug group used among Method of drug use is consider as a game changer factor in pharmaceutical therapy, it have crucial role in controlling side and adverse effect. By using drug according to instruction given by health care professionals various type of problems can minimized, like drug drug interaction, drug food interaction and therapeutic failure. Result of this part explained that 82 students (38%) were usually followed the Instructions in package regarding the appropriate choice of specific OTC preparations, while the remaining 72 students (33%) were usually followed their own knowledge. And by asking peoples who previously used 38 students Extent of knowledge about side effect is very important for safe use of any OTC or prescribed drug. In present project knowledge level of participating about side effect was also judged, the finding revealed that 159 (73%) of participating

condition is mild. Finally 5 students (2%) using OTC because of expensive consultancy as shown in Figure 6.

students. Second most frequently used group was antibiotics 54 students (25%), further various frequencies of numerous drug group were founded, like cold and cough 39 students (18%), Antipyretics 23 students (11%), Vitamins 9 students (4%), Ant acids 2 students (1%), anti-anxiety, 1 students (0%) as shown in Figure 8.

The pattern, by which a consumer achieves medicine form pharmacy or medical store, is an important factor that effect prevalence of OTC consumed. In this work it was try to elucidate that by which method students achieve medicines from pharmacy or medical store. Result showed that the most common methods for selecting the preferred OTC drug were mentioning the brand name of an OTC drug 139 students (64%), followed by mentioning the generic name 32 students (15%), and also by mentioning the symptoms 27 students (12%), while the remaining students usually purchased the preferred OTC drug based on old prescription 20 students (9%), as shown in Figure 9.

(17%), by asking pharmacist in pharmacy 26 students (12%) as shown in Figure 10.

Any unwanted effect produce by taking the drug is called side effect, side effect usually disappear at stop of drug use. If effect persists even after cessation of therapy this unwanted effect is termed as adverse effect. Side and adverse effects play important role in success of any therapy, in present study presence or absence of side effect were also evaluated. From evaluations it was concluded that side-effects followed by use of OTC were experienced by 33% and 67% of theme not experience any side effects as shown in Figure 11. students were well aware about their expected side effects, while (27%) of them were unaware to the side effects of non-prescribed drugs as shown in Figure 12.

FIGURE 1- OTC medicines preference among IPS students.

FIGURE 2- OTC medicines preference among IPRS students.

FIGURE 3- Reasons to avoid self-medicine among studied students.

FIGURE 4- Weight frequency of participating students.

FIGURE 5- Residence for students using OTC drug.

FIGURE 6- Reasons for OTC drug preference among studied students.

FIGURE 7- Medical conditions that influence the choice of OTC medicines.

FIGURE 8- Drug group mostly use by study students.

FIGURE 9- Methods for selecting the preferred OTC medicines.

FIGURE 10- Methods for selecting the preferred OTC medicines.

FIGURE 11- Numbers of participating experienced side effects.

FIGURE 12- Knowledge of side effects.

DISCUSSION

People have always been extremely cautious about their health status, in order to assure this they have used self-medication, which is considered as a feature of healthcare from ancient times. Although self-medication has many pros and cons, it also depends upon conditions in which it has been used and how long, for self-treatment⁴. In 1981-World Medical Association take entrust in emphasizing the responsibility of people regarding their own health in a “Declaration on the Rights of the Patient”⁵.

In present study we focused on female medical students (Pharmacy and Physiotherapy), this might be due the fact that women believe to recognize the drugs as more powerful tool and they considers prevention and treatment are more effective than men. Studies shows that educated population, particularly students belonging to health care programs are more prone to take self-medication, because they have adequate theoretical and practical knowledge of medicine. The students of health care programs considers that they have sound knowledge about safe and effective use of medicines, that’s why they are more prone to take self-medication in comparison to other population.

In developing countries, the usage of OTC medications has been introduced into practice for several reasons, for example lacking of rules and regulation regarding purchasing and selling of medications, people feel ease to self-medicate the conditions based on their previous experiences, negligence, and poverty to some extent⁷.

Socioeconomic factors, lifestyle, availability of drugs, unaffordable medical consultation cost, time consuming clinical process, lack of nearby healthcare units, previous experiences and frequent advertisement are some of the leading reasons for people self-medication.

Results of present study revealed that, 68% respondent female students used medication without suggestion of health care professionals. A similar type of study was conducted in a study, which found prevalence of self-medication prevalence 62.9% and 79.9% respondents used medication without doctor’s advice⁵.

In addition, the present study was conducted among different age groups; the distribution of age was as following: below 20 years (11%), 21–23 years (65%) and above 23 years (24%). In present survey significant portion (32%) among studied population refuse to use OTC medicine, it has been found that main reason were fear of side effects (51%) followed by the believe that it may be injurious to health, the mentioned reasons may be related to fact that they are studding in medical university and they experienced many cases related to adverse drug effects. However, some features did not noticeably affect the student's refuse for OTC medications, such as lack of knowledge and any bed experience.

In present study same behavior for taking medicines by herself was found between hosteller and locale students, from survey it was found that among participants half of students were from hostel and same percentage from local area.

Results of this study showed that the common reason to use OTC medicine is prevention of known illness student already faced and they do not need any consultancy with physician or contact with pharmacist, further self-medication considered as time saving. Little number (2%) of participants believed that consultant fees showing any significant effect on OTC medicine use.

The results of this study shows that the most common medical conditions that influence the choice of OTC medications among the students were headache (67%) of total studied population. These results are almost comparable with another study⁹. Among the studied population next common reasons to take self-medication were found common cold, and cough these results are comparable with other studies⁴.

Significant portion (41%) of self-medication was found to include the analgesics, almost same percentage (49.59%) were found in a study previously conducted, result of a study also revealed that analgesics were most frequently self-taking medicine^{3,6}. Results of a study also revealed that use of antibiotics and drug for cold and cough were 25% & 18% respectively¹⁰. High antibiotic behavior in students also shown in different studies as in a study conducted in university students in Abbottabad Pakistan, indicate that

70% of students uses antibiotics in cold and flu because antibiotics are easily available in Pakistan without prescription¹.

Results of present work showed that the majority of students were preferred to purchase OTC drug. In this study the source of medicine information was found leaflets and their own academic knowledge. Self-medication behavior by asking from seniors and health care profession had also contributed to it. Source of information about medication from peoples were also found in another study⁶.

This point should also be taken into account and policies makers and regulatory agencies should pay particular attention on prevention of self-medication of potent and dangerous drug by preparing Laws and effectively imposing of.

As self-medication is now increasing gradually it is also considered an integral part of self-care, there is an immense need for review of educational programs, particularly teaching of basic knowledge about clinical pharmacology, rational and judicious use of medicines. At policy making level, there is a vital need to design and reinforce laws regarding the use of antibiotics, antihistaminic and others Non OTC drugs. To educate the public about hazard, dangerous, side and adverse effects arise from self-medication is a keen need of time, in order to ensure the safe and effective use of drugs.

CONCLUSION

An extensive evaluation has been conducted about factors affecting the use of OTC drugs. From results it was concluded that most of student use the drug on the base of previous successful experience. Self-use of drug is not safe in any condition, because from latest pharmacogenomics studies it has been found that each drug produce unique effect in individual body, it mean one drug may effective for a person may not effective for other. So frequent use of OTC drugs should minimized by effective law and promoting the education of society.

via mentioning the Brand name, while little number of students purchase the medicine by generic name.

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